

Image and Vision Computing

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Graphical Abstract (Optional)

HDD-Unet: A Unet-based architecture for low-light image enhancement

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HDD-Unet: A Unet-based architecture for low-light image enhancement

We have a low-light images collection and normal light images collection as input in a double Unet architecture

- Use a new double-branch Unet based architecture
- Include a Haar wavelet-based pooling layer to capture surface and texture information more effectively
- Including histogram color to further improve the generated color information
- Combines densely connected convolutional blocks for image denoising.
- Fuse the outputs of both branches to generate the final enhanced output.
- Demonstrate its effectiveness on a range of low light imaging scenarios

Random selected outputs from the proposed approach

In conclusion, the proposed approach:

- Generates a normal light from a given low-light image
- Preserves the content and color information
- Has less distortions and noise which deform the output
- Reach and in many cases outperforms the SoA
- Significantly less computational resources without sacrificing image quality
- Could be used on a range of low light imaging scenarios

Graphical Abstract

Research Highlights (Required)

- Low-light image enhancement based on a combination of two U-Net branches with wavelet transformations, Adaptive Instance Normalization, color histogram blocks and denoising dense blocks
- Analytic framework creation for the HDD-Unet architecture
- Evaluation of the proposed method in a qualitative and a quantitative way.

HDD-Unet: A Unet-based architecture for low-light image enhancement

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Abstract

Low-light imaging has become a popular topic in image processing, with the quality enhancement of low light images being a significant challenge, due to the difficulty in retaining colors, patterns, texture and style when generating a normal light image. Our objectives are mainly to firstly better preserve texture regions in image enhancement, while, secondly, preserving colors via color histogram blocks and, finally, to enhance the quality of image through dense denoising blocks. Our proposed novel framework, namely HDD-Unet, is a double Unet based on photorealistic style transfer for low-light image enhancement. The proposed low-light image enhancement method combines color histogram-based fusion, Haar wavelet pooling, dense-denoising blocks and U-net as a backbone architecture to enhance the contrast, reduce noise, and improve the visibility of low light images. Experimental results demonstrate that our proposed method outperforms existing methods in terms of PSNR and SSIM quantitative evaluation metrics, reaching or outperforming state-of-the-art accuracy, but with less resources. We also conduct an ablation study to investigate the impact of our approach on overexposed images, and systematic analysis on the late fusion weighting parameters. Multiple experiments were conducted with artificial noise inserted to accomplish more efficient comparison. The results show that the proposed framework enhances accurately images with various gamma corrections. The proposed method represents a significant advance in the field of low light image enhancement and has the potential to address several challenges associated with low light imaging.

Keywords: low-light image, image enhancement, Unet, Haar pooling, wavelet pooling, denoising, color histogram blocks, fusion.

1. Introduction

Low light imaging has many practical applications, such as surveillance, automotive imaging, and medical imaging, where it is often necessary to acquire images in low-light conditions. However, low-light images are usually characterized by low brightness, low contrast, a narrow gray range, color distortion and severe noise exists,

which can make it difficult to extract useful information. Hence, the generation of normal-light images from given low-light images, is an essential issue for image processing due to its extensive applicability.

Various techniques have been proposed recently, due to the increased interest of the community, including traditional methods based on gray level transformation [1], histogram equalization [2], and Retinex-based methods [3], as well as more advanced methods based on machine learning[4], deep learning [5], and image fusion [6], aiming to improve texture, brightness, contrast and color-like information. However, photorealistic style transfer has not yet fully unlocked its potential in generating normal light images from a given low-light input. In addition, it

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is not adequate to reconstruct an image from a low-light input focusing only on patterns and texture, but also it is necessary to reveal hidden color information out of low contrast and luminance.

In this paper, we propose a novel low-light image enhancement architecture that is based on two modified U-Net [7] based branches. The first branch involves dense blocks [8], which contain dense, convolutional, and wavelet pooling layers [9] to better preserve texture regions in image enhancement. Similar to the first branch, the second additionally includes histogram color blocks [10] to preserve color information, and also dense denoising blocks [11] to enhance the image further. The outputs of both branches are combined to generate an enhanced normal light output for the overall framework in a late fusion manner. The proposed low-light image enhancement architecture is based on photorealistic style transfer and requires as input low-light and normal-light images during the training procedure, where encoding is using low frequency components and unpooling is performed with high frequency components, which leads to better image enhancement [9]. Normal-light images are incorporated during the training phase to guide the enhancement of low-light images by providing a reference for learning the desired output. This supervised learning approach enables the model to map low-light inputs to enhanced outputs that match the quality of normal-light images. In the testing phase, however, unpaired normal-light images were used as input to facilitate the style transfer process, ensuring that the model produces natural, high-quality results. These normal-light images do not serve as ground truth but provide a reference for enhancing low-light images. The unpaired input ensures the generalization of the model and enhances low-light images without the necessity of processing paired normal-light ground truth during the testing process. Moreover, the second branch accepts a normal light input image and a target histogram to produce an output image with the fine details of the input image, but with the same color distribution given in the target histogram.

Overall, the main contributions of the proposed method can be summarized as follows:

- We propose a novel architecture to generate enhanced images acquired under low-light conditions, by both maximizing the information involved from

the input image on the available patterns, and extracting the color information from the low values of luminance.

- In the proposed framework we further improve the generated color information by including histogram color blocks on a double-branch U-net architecture.
- The new architecture combines densely connected convolutional blocks, reusing feature maps within the encoder and decoder for image denoising.
- We demonstrate its effectiveness on a range of low light imaging scenarios and show that it can significantly improve the quality of low light images in practical settings.

In summary, the proposed HDD-Unet method addresses the challenges of preserving fine details, enhancing colors, reducing noise, and balancing computational efficiency in low-light image enhancement. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a review of related work on low light image enhancement. Section 3 describes our proposed method in detail. Section 4 presents the experimental results and performance analysis, along with an ablation study. Finally, Section 5 presents an ablation study and Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Related Work

Low-light image enhancement has evolved from statistical techniques like histogram equalization to modern deep learning approaches, including Retinex-based methods and convolutional neural networks.

Earlier methods like histogram equalization [12] enhanced contrast by adjusting the pixel intensity range but often introduced artifacts and ignored local pixel correlations, leading to visual distortions [2].

Retinex theory [13] improves on histogram methods by computing lightness values that correlate with human perception, enabling better handling of illumination and reflectance. Retinex-based approaches [14, 15] enhance illumination and reflectance estimation, but often rely on simplified illumination maps, which can introduce artifacts. Li et al. [3] proposed a Retinex model that addresses the issue of noise in estimating the illumination

map. The proposed method involves solving an optimization problem to generate an image with high contrast, while ensuring proper tonal rendition and luminance in every region. Furthermore, Lee et al. [16] introduced an adaptive multi-scale Retinex approach for image enhancement. An image enhancement framework has been obtained in some recent works by combining the camera response and the conventional Retinex model, as mentioned in [17]. Retinex theory has been reconsidered as an alternative to techniques that alter the distribution of image histograms or rely on physical models. Retinex-Net [18], separates input images into reflectance and illumination, using an encoder-decoder network to modify the illumination. In contrast to Retinex-based methods combined with neural networks to enhance images, these methods can produce fuzzy artifacts that impair the quality of the generated images.

With the advent of deep learning, various techniques have been proposed for enhancing images. Deep learning techniques offer several advantages over Retinex in terms of automation, scalability, flexibility, and performance. In [5], a deep architecture entitled as LLNet was proposed to improve light distribution. Another neural network for low-light image enhancement is MSRNet [19] which can directly learn the mapping from low-light to normal light images in an end-to-end fashion through an optimization problem. In [20], the authors present another end-to-end convolutional neural network for enhancing under-exposed images, in which the network includes an illumination layer, estimating the image-to-illumination mapping, aiming to model various lighting conditions. While deep learning models [5, 19, 20] outperform traditional methods, they often neglect color preservation and noise reduction, challenges directly addressed by our proposed HDD-Unet through its dual-branch architecture combining color histogram and denoising blocks. A different neural network architecture for image enhancement was introduced in [21] that comprises of two layers. The first layer slices data into a bilateral grid, while the second layer computes the grid and predicts local affine color transformations through a multiplicative operation. A Global illumination-Aware and Detail-preserving Network (GLADNet) is introduced in [22] that also consists of two stages; downsampling and global illumination prediction in the first stage, followed by a reconstruction step to recover lost details. Furthermore, in [23], a residual

convolutional neural network is trained using a translation function to enhance both color rendition and image sharpness. Recent multi-stage networks [22, 23] focus on illumination prediction, but they often overlook critical aspects of texture and color restoration. A trainable convolutional neural network named LightenNet [24] is introduced for enhancing weak illumination images by learning the relationship between illuminated images and their corresponding illumination maps. All these methods propose a novel deep neural network architecture as the backbone part of the methodological approach, and they were used as baselines to build more recent approaches in the following years.

Recent works in low-light image enhancement introduce more advanced architectures with additional features. In [25], a low-light enhancement network is introduced that employs a feature spatial pyramid model. The image is first decomposed into reflection and illumination images and then fused together to obtain the enhanced image. In [26], a method for enhancing low-light images based on flow has been introduced. The method determines the appropriate conditional distribution of the enhanced images, allowing it to learn the local pixel correlations and global image properties. Moreover, the approach of [27] involves extracting first-order and second-order gradient information from low-light images and combining them with the images to perform multi-view feature analysis within the multi-view fusion encoder (MFE). Additionally, the multi-branch topology module (MTM) is proposed to merge and decompose the multi-view features. Ultimately, the multi-view features are reconstructed through the multi-view decomposition decoders (MDDs), which consist of three sub-decoders, to produce possibly normal-light images. Moreover, the proposed network of [28], called MTRBNet, utilizes a multi-branch topological residual block (MTRB) to facilitate information flow between convolutional units. Furthermore, in [29], the authors present a low-illumination enhancement algorithm that can enhance a single low-illumination image input. Firstly, they propose a two-stage low-illumination image restoration network that includes a pre-decomposition submodule. Secondly, they introduce a novel loss function that guides the decomposition network to focus on the dark area of the image. Our previous work [30] proposed an approach that utilizes a modified U-Net architecture with dense blocks

and wavelet pooling layers. In our approach, the low frequency (LL) component is used for encoding while decoding is performed using the high frequency components (LH, HL, HH) of the input image. This allows the proposed approach to preserve the structural and textural information by employing wavelet pooling transformation.

Motivated by the good performance of neural networks, but at a higher computational cost, generative adversarial networks (GANs) combine two neural networks and have also been involved in image enhancement. The proliferation of GANs has resulted in numerous image enhancement methods that strive to eliminate the need for paired data during training. The authors in [31] proposed an adversarial learning approach for image enhancement called EnhanceGAN. They demonstrated the effectiveness of a color enhancement module trained with weak supervision and also extended the proposed framework to learn a deep filtering-based aesthetic enhancer. Furthermore, the approach presented in [32] utilizes an unpaired learning method, employing a two-way GAN architecture similar to CycleGAN but with significant modifications. The modifications include augmenting the U-Net architecture with global features, enhancing the Wasserstein GAN [33] with an adaptive weighting scheme, and incorporating individual batch normalization layers for generators in two-way GANs. Zero-DCE [4], generates high-order tonal curves from low-light images as output, which are utilized for pixel-wise adjustment on the input range to achieve the enhanced image. Additionally, Le-GAN [34] incorporates an illumination-aware attention module and an identity invariant loss. The authors of [35] proposed an unsupervised approach using the bright channel prior (BCP) to enhance low-light images, combining saturation loss and a self-attention map to preserve image details. In addition, EnlightenGAN [36], addresses low-light image enhancement by utilizing a one-way GAN and a global-local discriminator structure. However, a common issue with these methods is that they tend to enhance the overall brightness of the input, leading to over-exposed regions in the generated output a limitation addressed by our HDD-UNet’s balanced enhancement process.

3. Methodology

In this section we present the proposed architecture, which combines two U-net based branches with wavelet

transformations (Section 3.1), Adaptive Instance Normalization (AdaIN), color histogram blocks (Section 3.3) and denoising dense blocks (Section 3.4) as it is illustrated in Fig. 1.

In detail, the presented framework of Fig. 1 combines two U-Net branches to preserve spatial information, incorporating a multi-layer feature aggregation (MFA) [8] to extract details from low-level layers during the image enhancement. The second U-net branch (B) is enriched with color histogram blocks to control the colors of images generated by the proposed HDD-UNet and with dense denoising blocks to remove the noise and generate an enhanced output image. The architecture of each branch (A and B) is described in Section 3.1. The outputs from both U-nets are fused to generate the final enhanced output. The enhanced images are generated by the framework using a combination of low-light and normal-light images as its input. Subsequently, dense blocks are employed to improve the quality of feature transfer, along with skip connections during the feature transfer process.

3.1. HDD-UNet architecture

The proposed architecture is comprised by two U-net based branches, where each is constituted by the following three sub-components: encoder, decoder and enhancer. To ensure the structural integrity of an image we follow the U-Net architecture [7] with a symmetrical structure consisting of both encoder and decoder. Both U-net-based branches’s encoders consist of convolutional and pooling layers that utilize downsampling, whereas the decoder components implement an upsampling mechanism that is aligned with the encoders. A skip connection is incorporated in both U-Net branches, linking the encoders with the corresponding decoder modules. Inspired of the UMFA [8] Photorealistic Style Transfer module, the enhancer includes multi-layer feature aggregation (MFA) and AdaIN blocks [37], in addition to the existing skip connections. The network’s encoder and enhancer modules are equipped with Haar wavelet-based pooling layers (Down Dense block and AdaIN block, reducing the feature size by one half), which serve to capture both texture and smooth surface information as it is proposed in [30], in contrast to the conventional max-pooling layer. In addition, the second U-net branch (B) also includes a color histogram block where color features are extracted from the input normal light image and sent as input to AdaIN

Figure 1: Proposed low-light image enhancement framework with two U-net based branches.

block during the decoding process. Moreover, there exists a set of dense denoising blocks in both encoder and decoder modules. Fig. 1 illustrates the normal-light and low-light image features through the red and blue solid lines, respectively. The Haar wavelet-based pooling is

integrated into the dense blocks of the encoder and the AdaIn block of the enhancer module. Moreover, the pink lines represent the color features of the normal-light images.

Branch A: Branch A of the proposed framework is

comprised by three sub-components namely encoder, enhancer and decoder. The encoder includes convolutional layers and downsampling dense blocks. The downsampling dense blocks include a Haar wavelet-based pooling layer, a dense block, and two convolutional layers. A dense block is comprised of three convolutional layers that are densely connected. The Haar wavelet pooling layer transformations perform downsampling operations that halve the feature size while maintaining the same dimensions as a max pooling layer. By incorporating the encoder, multi-scale image information can be preserved, and high-resolution images can be processed. Concerning the decoder, it is structured similarly to the encoder and is used to form a U-Net along with the aforementioned encoder. The decoder contains four upsampling blocks, each of which includes an upsampling layer, three convolutional layers, and a concatenation operation that receives the corresponding encoder feature from the enhancer module. Regarding the enhancer module, it transmits multi-scale features from the encoder to the decoder, allowing the network to integrate spatial information from different scales while maintaining the input image’s detailed information. The features from each pair of layers in the encoder are added to the next layer and then transformed with AdaIN to improve the input image’s quality. Additionally, the module utilizes the Haar wavelet transformation-based pooling layer, which is described briefly in sub-section 3.2.

Branch B: Branch B of the proposed framework consists of the identical sub-components as branch A, while additionally incorporating supplementary features in encoding and decoding to enhance its functionality. The encoder of branch B is enriched with the color histogram blocks and dense denoising blocks which are detailed in sub-sections 3.3 and 3.4 respectively. Similarly, the decoder of the U-net branch B also includes the dense denoising blocks of its corresponding encoder.

Finally, the outputs of branch A and branch B are fused as it is described in sub-section 3.5 to generate the final enhanced output of the HDD-Unet framework.

3.2. Haar wavelet pooling

In order to capture surface and texture information more effectively, the Haar wavelet-based pooling layer is utilized as a replacement for the traditional max-pooling layer. Haar wavelet pooling has four kernels,

$\{LL^T, LH^T, HL^T, HH^T\}$, where the low (L) and high (H) pass filters are:

$$L^T = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [1 \ 1] \quad (1)$$

$$H^T = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [-1 \ 1] \quad (2)$$

The Haar wavelet-based pooling generates four channels: LL, LH, HL, and HH, each corresponding to the output of a kernel. These channels provide different types of information. Specifically, the low-pass filter LL captures smooth surface and texture, whereas the high-pass filters (LH, HL, HH) extract edge-like information in different directions such as vertical, horizontal, and diagonal. The technique proposed in [30] utilizes wavelet pooling instead of max-pooling at every downsampling step. Inspired by [9], the wavelet pooling replaces the conventional max-pooling layers, and the resultant low-frequency component (LL) is propagated to the subsequent encoding layer. The encoder uses wavelet pooling, where the low frequency component (LL) is passed to the next encoding layer, while the high frequency components (LH, HL, HH) are skipped to the decoder. By using wavelet pooling, the original vector can be accurately reconstructed through a component-wise transposed-convolution, followed by a summation. Haar wavelet, which is a simple wavelet transformation, separates the original signal into channels that capture distinct components.

3.3. Color histogram blocks

To enhance the color performance of the proposed architecture in the presence of low-lighting conditions, a feature that is generated from the histogram distribution is employed. This histogram-based feature is designed to be differentiable and constructed in the log-chroma space, providing improved invariance to changes in illumination [10]. By projecting an image’s colors into a log-chroma space, the histogram color feature generates a 2D histogram that is parameterized by “uv”. This histogram represents an image’s color information in a more condensed form compared to a typical 3D histogram defined in RGB space.

To create a log-chroma space, one color channel’s intensity I_R , is normalized by the intensities of the other two

Figure 2: The frameworks of Down Dense Blocks; Up Convolutional Blocks; Multi Feature Aggregate; Dense Blocks and Denoising Dense Blocks of framework of Fig. 1

channels I_G and I_B as it is defined below in Eq.3.

$$\begin{aligned} I_{uR}(x) &= \log((I_R + \epsilon)/(I_G + \epsilon)), \\ I_{vR}(x) &= \log((I_R + \epsilon)/(I_B + \epsilon)) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where R, G, and B refer to the RGB color channels of the input image I , ϵ is a small constant added to avoid numerical errors and the calculation to remain stable, x is the pixel index, and (uR, vR) are the uv coordinates based on using R as the primary channel.

Similarly, for creating a log-chroma space for green and blue, the intensity I_G (I_B) is normalized by the intensities of I_R and I_B (I_R and I_G) channels. This normalization process can be performed in three distinct ways, resulting in three possible definitions of the log-chroma space. The logarithmic scale of the resulting space facilitates the representation of chromaticity and provides a better approximation of how humans perceive colors.

All three different combinations of I_R , I_G , I_B are employed to create three different histograms, which are combined together into a histogram feature, H , as an $h \times h \times 3$ tensor of Eq. (6). The histogram is computed from a given input image I , by first converting it into the log-chroma space and the final unnormalized histogram is computed as follows:

$$H(u, v, R) \propto \sum_x k(I_{uR}(x), I_{vR}(x), u, v) I_y(x) \quad (4)$$

$$H(u, v, G) \propto \sum_x k(I_{uG}(x), I_{vG}(x), u, v) I_y(x) \quad (5)$$

$$H(u, v, B) \propto \sum_x k(I_{uB}(x), I_{vB}(x), u, v) I_y(x) \quad (6)$$

where $k(\cdot)$ is a pre-defined kernel and

$$I_y(x) = \sqrt{I_R^2(x) + I_G^2(x) + I_B^2(x)} \quad (7)$$

The color histogram features are extracted early in the process, specifically after the first dense denoising block. The features capture the color distribution of the low-light image and serves as a guide for preserving color information during enhancement. The extracted color features are fused with image features through Adaptive Instance Normalization (AdaIN) and skip connections in the decoder. By using the AdaIN mechanism, the color histogram features are seamlessly integrated into the image features, allowing the enhanced image to maintain both structural and color fidelity. The term 'recoloring generated image' refers to the process where color information, derived from the color histogram blocks, is reintroduced into the enhanced image. Although not a separate module, this recoloring occurs during the decoding phase, where color features are extracted from the low-light image, processed through color histogram blocks, and applied to enhance the final output image. This ensures that the final generated image retains natural and consistent color information despite the low-light input.

3.4. Dense denoising blocks

At each level, there is a denoising block in the encoding and decoding stages for further image enhancement given the fact that in every generated image we observe a significant amount of noise. An important aspect of the dense denoising block is the residual learning, in which the output of a layer is added to the input of the other layer, rather than replacing it entirely. This ensures that the network optimizes residual mappings and not direct mappings ensuring that important information from previous layers is preserved and passed along to subsequent layers. The architecture of the dense denoising block is shown in Fig. 2.

3.5. Fusion

In the late fusion part of our framework we combine the generated images from each branch. Our objective is to generate a single output image that provides more comprehensive and accurate information than any of the two individual input images. We adopt the common weighted sum approach, where each input image is assigned a weight that reflects its relative importance in the fused image. In this approach, the pixel values of the output image are calculated as a weighted sum of the corresponding pixel values in the input images. In detail, the branch output A and B are denoted by O_A and O_B , respectively, and by E the enhanced output image. The weighted fusion is defined by

$$E = w * O_A + (1 - w) * O_B \quad (8)$$

In the proposed architecture the weights w are determined by the PSNR values [38]. The resulting fused image provides a more informative representation of the underlying scene and improve the reliability of subsequent image analysis. An ablation study for PSNR and SSIM values covering different w and luminance values is presented in Section 5.

3.6. Loss functions

Based on [8], the total loss function of the branch A L_{total} is computed as a weighted sum of enhancement loss, content loss and structured similarity (SSIM) loss, respectively:

$$L_{total} = \alpha L_{enh} + \beta L_{cont} + \gamma L_{SSIM} \quad (9)$$

where L_{cont} and L_{SSIM} are computed between the input low-light content image and the enhanced output image. L_{enh} is the enhancement loss between the input normal-light image and the generated output image as it is presented in [8]. L_{cont} and L_{enh} are based on the perceptual loss that has been defined in [39]. The parameters α, β, γ are the weights of the above three losses. For the content loss, the $relu_{2,2}$ is chosen as the feature layer. The SSIM loss is calculated as follows:

$$L_{SSIM} = 1 - SSIM(C, E) \quad (10)$$

where $SSIM(C, E)$ represents the output of structural similarity (SSIM) [38] measure between the input low-light content image C and generated image E . The SSIM model is designed to consider crucial perceptual information, such as luminance and contrast terms, thereby making it a perception-based approach.

Although the main objective of the total loss that corresponds to branch A is to enhance the image focusing on the content, texture and pattern information, the total loss of branch B introduces color information. Concerning the branch B of the HDD-Unet the total loss function L_{total} is computed as a pre-defined weighted sum of enhancement loss, content loss, structured similarity (SSIM) loss functions and color-matching histogram loss function.

$$L_{total} = \kappa L_{enh} + \lambda L_{cont} + \mu L_{SSIM} + \nu L_{color} \quad (11)$$

where L_{cont} , L_{SSIM} and L_{enh} are computed as in the first branch A 9. The parameters κ, λ, μ and ν represent the weights of the above four losses.

Aiming at generating images that match the input low-light image's color histogram, a color matching loss is introduced [10]. L_{color} is the color-matching histogram loss function between the input normal-light image and the enhanced output image. We denote by H_{out} as the histogram of the output image and by H_{nl} the histogram of the normal light image. Due to the differentiability of the histogram representation [10], the loss function, $L_{color}(H_{out}, H_{nl})$, can be any differentiable metric of similarity between the generated and target normal light histograms H_{out} and H_{nl} , therefore, we are also based in [10] on the use of Hellinger distance defined as:

$$L_{color}(H_{out}, H_{nl}) = (1/\sqrt{2}) \|H_{out}^{(1/2)} - H_{nl}^{(1/2)}\|_2 \quad (12)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_2$ is the Euclidean norm and $H^{(1/2)}$ is an element wise square root.

4. Experimental Results

This section provides in-depth insights into the experimental configurations adopted for our research study, as well as the qualitative and quantitative validation methods used to compare the results with state-of-the-art methods. The experimental configurations encompass various parameters that are crucial for the accurate implementation of the proposed model, including the selection of batch size, learning rate, and number of epochs. The qualitative and quantitative validation methods provide an objective assessment of the proposed method’s performance, ensuring the reliability and reproducibility of the results. The quantitative validation measures include image quality metrics, such as peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) and structural similarity index (SSIM). On the other hand, the qualitative validation methods encompass human evaluations of the visual quality of the enhanced images, as well as comparisons with SoA techniques. By leveraging these comprehensive experimental configurations and validation methods, our research study provides a thorough assessment of the proposed method’s performance, compared to the other relevant SoA.

4.1. Datasets

Benchmark datasets were used to evaluate the performance of relevant methods to improve lighting quality of the processed images. These datasets provide a standardized set of images for researchers to use, ensuring that comparisons between different methods are fair and unbiased.

To evaluate performance on low-light and enhanced images, two benchmark datasets were utilized: LOL [18] and SYN [18]. Both of these datasets are designed to be challenging, with a wide range of low-light conditions and variations in color, contrast, and noise. The LOL Dataset consists of 500 image pairs (485 for training, 15 for validation), where each low-light image is paired with a corresponding ground truth normal-light image. The images cover a variety of indoor and outdoor scenes under different lighting conditions, providing a comprehensive evaluation environment for enhancement

methods. Moreover, the SYN Dataset contains 1,000 synthetic image pairs (950 for training, 50 for testing). This dataset is designed to simulate low-light conditions by synthetically darkening normal-light images. The SYN dataset is useful for analyzing the robustness of the enhancement algorithms under controlled conditions, allowing for systematic comparison with state-of-the-art methods. These datasets are selected for their ability to assess the model’s performance in both real-world and synthetic low-light scenarios, ensuring a well-rounded evaluation of the proposed method. The LOL dataset focuses on real-world challenges, while the SYN dataset allows for a more controlled experimental setup to validate generalization and robustness. We use exactly the given training and testing instances, for both datasets, for a fair comparison with the community that uses LOL and SYN datasets [18]. Additionally, experiments were conducted with additional benchmark datasets including NPE [40], LIME [15], MEF [41], VV¹ and DICM [42]. These datasets are widely used in low-light image enhancement research and consist of various challenging low-light images. However, these datasets do not provide corresponding ground truth normal-light images, making it impossible to calculate quantitative metrics such as PSNR and SSIM. Despite the lack of ground truth, these datasets are valuable for evaluating the visual performance of low-light enhancement methods in real-world scenarios. To address this, we provide a set of figures where we compare qualitatively the result of our method with SoA.

4.2. Training process

The training process is initiated by feeding each branch of the model with the normal-light and the corresponding low-light images that are given from each dataset. For both datasets, for the first branch A, the weights for total loss was set as $\alpha = 0.5$, $\beta = \gamma = (1 - \alpha) * 0.5$ following the default values of [8]. Furthermore the weights for the total loss for the second branch B was set as $\kappa = 0.7$, $\lambda = \mu = \nu = 0.1$. Similarly, concerning the first branch A, the number of epochs is set to 150 for the LOL dataset and 100 for the SYN dataset, because SYN dataset has more images to be utilized for the training. Nonetheless

¹<https://github.com/Elin24/Awesome-Low-Light-Enhancement?tab=readme-ov-file>

Figure 3: Qualitative comparison of the proposed framework with state-of-the-art on SYN dataset.

the number of epochs for the second branch B is set to 60 for both datasets, optimized with respect to PSNR. The batch size is set to 4 for both datasets and branches, and all input images are 256×256 pixels in size. Adam optimizer is used for training and the optimal learning rate is 0.0001. Our experiments were performed on the NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2060 SUPER.

4.3. Evaluation metrics

To assess the quality of the enhanced images, we utilize two widely adopted metrics: Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) [38]. PSNR quantifies the difference between the enhanced image and the ground truth, with higher values indicating

better image fidelity. It is particularly useful for evaluating how well the method preserves image detail. SSIM, on the other hand, measures the perceived quality by comparing structural information such as luminance, contrast, and textures between the original and enhanced images. Both metrics are critical for assessing the visual and quantitative performance of low-light image enhancement techniques.

The PSNR is calculated as follows:

$$PSNR = 20 * \log_{10}(MAX_I) - 10 * \log_{10}(MSE) \quad (13)$$

where MAX_I is the maximum possible pixel value, MSE is the Mean Squared Error, defined as the average of the squared differences between the original and reconstructed image pixel values. The PSNR value is typically

Figure 4: Qualitative comparison of the proposed framework with state-of-the-art on LOL dataset.

expressed in decibels (dB), and a higher PSNR value indicates a higher quality image.

The SSIM index is then calculated as the product of these three components:

$$SSIM(I_1, I_2) = [l(I_1, I_2) * c(I_1, I_2) * s(I_1, I_2)] \quad (14)$$

where, I_1 and I_2 are the two input images being compared. $l(I_1, I_2)$, $c(I_1, I_2)$, and $s(I_1, I_2)$ are the local measures of luminance, contrast, and structure similarity, respectively.

4.4. Results

The baseline methods of the presented comparison are the histogram equalization methods of [44, 2], the Retinex theory based methods of [15, 3, 18, 16, 17, 14], the neural network approaches of [24, 43, 25, 22], the GANs based approaches of [34, 4, 36] and the approach of [30] due to their relevance to low-light image enhancement problem as they comprise types of the most common solutions. The proposed approach is denoted in Table 1 and Fig.3 as "HDD-Unet".

4.4.1. Quantitative evaluation

A quantitative evaluation is provided in Table 1, where the proposed approach is compared with the aforementioned methods for LOL and SYN datasets, as they were reported in [34, 25]. The PSNR scores correspond to the average value of the complete test set of enhanced images in LOL and SYN datasets. In Table 1, we observe that the highest PSNR values for each image test of LOL dataset correspond to the output of [47] and the proposed framework. PSNR values show that the generated images from the proposed approach obtain higher proximity to the input normal-light images than the imaged generated by all other methods. Concerning the SYN dataset the highest PSNR values correspond to the proposed approach and the approaches of [34, 47, 46], but our proposed approach is significantly more computationally efficient than Le-GAN. As shown in Table 1, our method has a significantly shorter training time of 13.8 hours, compared to 25.6 hours for the Le-GAN method using 3 NVIDIA 3090ti GPUs. Additionally, our method requires only 8GB of memory, whereas Le-GAN requires a

Figure 5: Qualitative comparison of the proposed framework with state-of-the-art on unpaired datasets.

Figure 6: More qualitative comparison of the proposed framework with state-of-the-art on unpaired datasets.

Figure 7: More qualitative comparison of the proposed framework with state-of-the-art on LOL dataset.

massive 3*24GB (standard Memory of 3 NVIDIA 3090ti) of memory. Moreover, our method also outperforms Le-GAN in terms of execution time. Execution time of HDD-Unet for one 600x400 image is 8.1ms, whereas the execution time of Le-GAN is estimated to be around 8.43ms. These results show that our proposed approach is not only more computationally efficient than Le-GAN but also requires significantly less computational resources without sacrificing image quality. This makes HDD-Unet more practical for real-world applications where computational efficiency and resource usage are essential. As far as SSIM value is concerned, the outputs of the presented framework on LOL dataset is on top-5 higher scores and on SYN dataset the outputs have comparable results with other state-of-the-art methods such as [30, 22].

4.4.2. Qualitative evaluation

In Figs 3, 4 and 7, we present qualitative low-light image enhancement results of the proposed HDD-Unet compared with other methods on the SYN and LOL dataset respectively. It is observed that the proposed method accurately reconstruct the hidden information of the low-light input image, while at the same time effectively increase the brightness, color information and decrease the noise.

Moreover, the proposed approach performs well in both datasets with nearly no artifacts and generates quite realistic normal-light images. This clearly indicates that the proposed model effectively disentangles the low-lightness from the content characteristics recovering any content and color details from the input images.

We compare our proposed method to many state-of-the-art works, as it is presented in Figs 4 and 3. In LOL dataset, it is observed that there are some bright regions of the results generated by the compared methods which are overexposed in the enhanced outputs. The proposed method produces consistent outputs and preserve certain attributes more advantageous than the state-of-the-art methods as is clear at the red boxes of each image. By contrast, as it is illustrated in Fig 7 the works of [28] and [27] results in inconsistent traversals that culminate in more unnatural generations compared with the ground truth. Additionally, experiments were conducted with NPE, LIME, MEF, VV and DICM datasets. In Fig. 5 we observe that our method’s results demonstrate notable improvements, even on unpaired datasets, with images that exhibit good illumination and minimal distortion of content. There are no blurry areas in the generated images, and many details are clearly visible, such as the feathers of

Table 1: Quantitative results on LOL and SYN datasets.

Methods	LOL		SYN		Execution times	
	PSNR	SSIM	PSNR	SSIM	training	testing
LDR [2]	15.484	0.634	13.187	0.591	-	-
LIME [15]	15.484	0.634	14.318	0.554	-	491.4ms
SRIE [14]	17.440	0.649	14.478	0.639	-	12.18s
GLADNet [22]	20.314	0.739	16.761	0.797	-	-
MTRBNet [28]	21.210	0.785	-	-	-	-
Retinex-Net [18]	17.780	0.425	16.286	0.779	-	120ms
EnlightenGAN [36]	18.850	0.736	16.073	0.827	-	7.8ms
Zero-DCE [4]	10.770	0.426	15.600	0.796	-	2.5ms
Le-GAN [34]	22.449	0.886	24.014	0.899	25.6h	8.43ms
Batzou et al. [30]	21.266	0.784	19.212	0.716	10.7h	5.27ms
RobustRetinex [3]	13.876	0.669	16.873	0.714	-	-
JED [43]	13.685	0.657	-	-	-	-
HE [44]	14.800	0.386	-	-	-	-
AMSR [16]	11.737	0.304	-	-	-	-
CRM [17]	12.327	0.472	-	-	-	-
LightenNet [24]	10.301	0.401	-	-	-	-
FSP [25]	19.347	0.751	-	-	-	-
GPANet [27]	20.862	0.784	-	-	-	-
two-stage network [29]	17.840	0.740	-	-	-	-
geometrical sparse [45]	20.0788	0.787	-	-	-	-
SNR [46]	21.480	0.849	24.014	0.928	-	-
Retinexformer [47]	22.800	0.840	25.670	0.930	-	-
HDD-Unet	22.657	0.783	20.221	0.711	13.8h	8.1ms

the swan in the last row of the Fig. 5, which are distinctly separated. However, there are some minor inaccuracies, as seen in the third row, where the sky appears uniformly colored, and the clouds are not distinguishable. In the next Fig 6, our method continues to perform well, with distinct details visible on the car and in the girl’s eyes. It handles the sky portion in the third row better, but it excels even further in rendering the wall’s patterns without distortion.

5. Ablation Study

In addition, a detailed sensitivity analysis was also performed for the adopted fusion scheme of the model we presented on the independent variable w . The purpose of this study is to validate the parameters that maximize the performance of the model by identifying the weights that produce the most accurate and high-quality fused output. The selected weights are based on k-fold cross validation for $k = 5$ on LOL dataset and the optimal value of w was adopted also for SYN dataset. To effectuate this outcome, we compute the PSNR and SSIM of the fused output for all possible values between $[0,1]$ on LOL dataset. By

computing the PSNR and SSIM values for multiple combinations of weights, we determined the optimal weights that result in the best overall performance for each dataset. This detailed analysis allows us to fine-tune the model for the fusion component, ultimately leading to improved performance and the optimal results with respect to PSNR and SSIM. The results are illustrated in Figures 9(a) and 9(b) for LOL and SYN datasets.

The fusion model analysis reveals a curvilinear relationship between the performance (PSNR in Fig 9(a) - SSIM in Fig 9(b)) of our model and the proportion of data from each branch. Through the process of graphically representing the individual data values on a coordinate system, using techniques such as line graphs, we observed a parabolic curve that fits the relationship between the two branches. Specifically, we ascertained that our fusion model’s performance improved as the proportion of data from one branch increased relative to the other branch, up to a certain point, after which further imbalance in the proportion led to diminishing returns. This finding indicates that there is an optimal proportion of data from each branch that results in the highest performance of our fusion model. The second-order curve can

Figure 8: Qualitative evolution of the images through the different gamma correction values on LOL dataset. The first and third rows show the under-exposed and over-exposed images, respectively, while the second and fourth rows are the corrected with our proposed HDD-Unet.

be used to estimate this optimal proportion and to predict the model’s performance for different proportions of data from each branch. This information is valuable for optimizing the performance of our fusion model without the need to run all possible experiments, and it can guide the allocation of resources towards the most effective data sources.

The quadratic relationship between the weight parameter w and the performance metrics (PSNR and SSIM) demonstrates that both Branch A and Branch B are critical to the network’s performance. Branch B, which includes both the color histogram blocks and dense denoising blocks, is responsible for handling color enhancement and denoising. In contrast, Branch A focuses on the primary image enhancement process, performing basic adjustments such as brightness and contrast corrections, without the detailed color and noise handling provided by Branch B. Values of the weight parameter w either close to 0 or to 1 are not optimal, showing that both branches are needed for optimal PSNR and SSIM results.

The performance curves, presented in 9, show that Branch A contributes to improve performance, but only

up to a certain point. Increasing the weight of Branch A relative to Branch B initially improves PSNR and SSIM, but eventually, further emphasis on Branch A leads to diminishing returns. This indicates that while Branch A is important for general enhancement, it cannot address the more complex challenges of low-light images (such as noise and color distortion) as effectively as Branch B.

Branch B, which includes the critical color and denoising modules, plays a key role in restoring color fidelity and reducing noise. As Branch B’s contribution increases, the performance metrics (particularly SSIM and PSNR) improve, indicating better perceptual quality and pixel-wise accuracy. The peak in the quadratic curve suggests that these modules are essential for maintaining high performance. However, beyond the optimal point, performance begins to decline, indicating that an over-reliance on Branch B at the expense of Branch A can also be sub-optimal.

The quadratic nature of the curves reflects that the best performance is achieved when there is a balance between Branch A and Branch B. Branch A provides general enhancement, while Branch B (with color and denoising

blocks) focuses on more specific improvements like noise reduction and color fidelity. The ablation experiments indicate that both branches are essential to the success of the HDD-Unet model. Branch B plays a crucial role in preserving color information and reducing noise, as reflected in the improvements in SSIM and PSNR. However, Branch A also makes significant contributions, and maintaining a balance between these two branches is key to achieving optimal performance. The quadratic relationship demonstrates that while Branch B is crucial for color and noise handling, an over-reliance on either branch leads to diminishing returns, emphasizing the need for a balanced approach to low-light image enhancement.

Furthermore, to provide a comprehensive analysis, we conducted a study to evaluate the performance of the presented model also in overexposed images for the purpose of completeness. Additionally, we provided qualitative results in Fig 8 to illustrate the corresponding performance of the model. By conducting this study, we were able to determine the effectiveness of the proposed model in handling overexposed images, which can provide valuable insights for future improvements and optimizations.

It involves applying a non-linear mapping function to the pixel values of an image, which alters the relationship between the intensity values and the resulting brightness of the image. The gamma value used in the correction determines the shape of the mapping function. The equation for gamma correction is described below:

$$I_{out} = I_{in}^{(1/\gamma)} \quad (15)$$

where I_{in} is the input pixel value, γ is the gamma value and I_{out} is the output pixel value after gamma correction.

We use different gamma correction values to create subsets out of the whole dataset. For each subset, one gamma value corresponds from 0.5 to 1.5, that generates images of various luminance values. In Figure 8 we present the evolution of generated images, while we are under- or over-exposing each of them, in parallel to the evolution of output images from our proposed model. We observe that in very under- or over-exposed inputs, the generated images are becoming more noisy, but color information and partially some patterns and texture tend to be preserved. In addition, we provide a comprehensive analysis of the performance of our proposed model across different

Figure 9: (a) PSNR for LOL and SYN datasets (b) SSIM for LOL and SYN datasets

gamma values in Fig 10. The Fig. 10 illustrates the plots of PSNR and SSIM metrics, demonstrating the model’s ability to preserve color information, patterns, and texture even under extreme under- or over-exposure.

Moreover we observe, based on Fig. 9, that there is a quadratic relationship between the weight parameter w and the performance metrics PSNR and SSIM. The parameter w quantifies the amount of branch A and B that need to be involved in the learning procedure, and has been introduced in Eq. 8. The perfect fit of PSNR and SSIM values to a quadratic model of $z_1w^2 + z_2w + z_3$ is shown in Table 2 where the R-squared values are very close to 1. This observation allows the optimisation of the weight parameter w as follows: $\hat{w} = -z_2/(2 * z_1)$ using only three measurements ($PSNR_i, w_i, i = 1, 2, 3$ or $SSIM_i, w_i, i = 1, 2, 3$).

Based on these results, we conclude that the proposed model shows promising performance across a range of luminance values, effectively handling challenging exposure conditions.

6. Conclusion

In this work, we propose a novel photorealistic style transfer approach that is modified to perform low-light image enhancement. The proposed architecture is built

Figure 10: PSNR and SSIM values for different gamma values: (a) PSNR values of LOL dataset, (b) SSIM values of LOL dataset, (c) PSNR values of SYN dataset, and (d) SSIM values of SYN dataset

Table 2: R-squared for various gamma values per dataset

gamma	LOL		SYN	
	PSNR	SSIM	PSNR	SSIM
0.5	0.9993	0.9991	0.9985	0.9713
0.6	0.9980	0.9997	0.9984	0.9786
0.7	0.9974	0.9990	0.9987	0.9738
0.8	0.9931	0.9992	0.9988	0.9679
0.9	0.9983	0.9986	0.9986	0.9770
1.1	0.9997	0.9995	0.9983	0.9671
1.2	0.9997	0.9995	0.9984	0.9952
1.3	0.9998	0.9984	0.9983	0.9972
1.4	0.9997	0.9981	0.9980	0.9960
1.5	0.9997	0.9959	0.9979	0.9956

upon two U-net branches that use dense blocks and are composed of three main modules: encoder, enhancer, and decoder. In both branches, the encoder and enhancer incorporate a Haar wavelet based pooling layer for down-sampling, which has been proven to extract superior results to max pooling in transferring brightness, contrast, and color-like information from one input to a generated image. Additionally, the second branch B of our architecture is enriched with histogram color features to improve color preservation, and dense denoising blocks for further enhancement. The outputs of the two branches are fused together to generate the final enhanced image. To evaluate the effectiveness of our approach, we conducted experiments on two benchmark datasets and compared our results with state-of-the-art methods. Specifically, we assessed the visual quality of the enhanced images using visual comparison, as well as quantitative metrics such as PSNR and SSIM. Our experimental results show that the proposed approach achieves or outperforms existing methods, while requiring fewer computational resources in both training and testing processes. Overall, the proposed method demonstrates the potential for photorealistic style transfer to be leveraged in low-light image enhancement, with the results indicating a significant improvement in image quality and computational efficiency.

The proposed HDD-Unet method effectively addresses several key challenges in low-light image enhancement, including improved detail preservation through dense denoising blocks, better color restoration via color histogram blocks, and a balanced trade-off between image quality and computational efficiency, making it suitable for real-time applications. Additionally, the method generalizes well across diverse low-light scenarios and datasets, demonstrating its robustness. However, further research should be conducted to explore specific aspects and address additional challenges. In extreme overexposure or highly uneven lighting conditions, artifacts may still appear, and the limited availability of large-scale unpaired datasets poses a challenge for further improving the model’s generalization capabilities. While HDD-Unet performs sufficiently in terms of quantitative metrics like PSNR and SSIM, these do not fully capture the perceptual quality of the enhanced images, indicating a need for future work that incorporates the definition of a novel human-centric metric. Additionally, in cases of severe or complex noise, the model’s denoising capabilities may

introduce slight blurring effects or fail to restore very fine details. Despite these challenges, HDD-Unet makes significant strides in low-light image enhancement, with space for further improvements in certain edge cases and perceptual quality.

The proposed HDD-Unet method has significant potential for advancing a variety of computer vision (CV) and computational imaging (CI) applications, particularly in environments with suboptimal lighting. In surveillance systems, HDD-Unet can enhance the visibility of low-light video feeds, improving object detection and security monitoring in nighttime conditions. Automotive vision systems can benefit from real-time low-light enhancement to ensure safer driving in poorly lit areas. Additionally, mobile photography can leverage the method to improve image quality without the need for additional hardware. Finally, drones and robots operating in low-visibility conditions (e.g. fog) could achieve better navigation and obstacle detection, enhancing their performance and safety in real-world scenarios. Overall, HDD-Unet's balance between image quality and computational efficiency makes it suitable for a wide range of practical applications.

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